

Synthesis of 4-Anilino 8-Hydroxy Quinolines

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4,7-Dichloro-8-aminoquinoline when treated with nitrous acid afforded 6,9-dichloro triazolo-(4,5,1-ij) quinoline-3-ium hydroxide, which on condensation with anilines gave the 7-chloro 4-anilino 8-hydroxy-quinolines.

It was considered to be of interest to synthesise some 4-aminoquinoline derivatives bearing a hydroxy group at the 8-position as possible antiamebic agents. Drake *et al.*¹, have reported that condensation of 4,7-dichloro-8-methoxy quinoline with novaldiamine gave 7-chloro-4 (4'-diethylamino-1'-methylbutyl amino)-8-hydroxyquinoline instead of the expected 8-methoxy derivative. 4,7-dichloro-8-methoxy quinoline also suffered partial demethylation during the isolation procedure following the treatment of the corresponding 4-hydroxy quinoline with phosphorus oxychloride².

Treatment of 4,7-dichloro-8-aminoquinoline with nitrous acid afforded 6,9-dichloro triazolo-(4,5,1-ij) quinoline-3-ium-hydroxide. The latter was smoothly transformed into known 4,7, 8-trichloroquinoline³ when subjected to Gatterman reaction condition and to 4,7-dichloro 8-hydroxy quinoline² on warming with mineral acids. The usual condensation of 4,7-dichloro-8-hydroxyquinoline or 6,9-dichloro triazolo (4,5,1—ij) quinoline-3-ium hydroxide with anilines gave the 7-chloro-4-anilino-8-hydroxyquinoline derivatives with simultaneous elimination of nitrogen in the latter case. An alternate synthesis involving treatment of 7-chloro-4-anilino 8-amino quinoline with nitrous acid gave identical products.

- IIa $R_1 = \text{OH}, R_2 = \text{H}$
 IIb $R_1 = \text{OCH}_3, R_2 = \text{H}$
 IIc $R_1 = \text{OH}, R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$

Condensation of novaldiamine with 6,9-dichloro triazolo (4,5,1-ij) quinoline 3-ium hydroxide led to a vigorous reaction with formation of tarry products from which we

1. Drake *et al.*, *Jour. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1208.
2. Lauer *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1946, 68, 1268.
3. Surrey and Hammer *ibid.*, 1946, 68, 1244.

were unable to isolate the desired compound, 7-chloro-4 (4'-diethylamino-1'-methylbutyl amino)-8-hydroxy quinoline.

In all condensation reactions high melting ethanol-insoluble products were always formed which were not investigated. The 8-hydroxy compounds readily forms metal chelates with a number of metal ions.

One of the commercial synthesis of 4,7-dichloro quinoline utilises the so-called oxaloacetic ester method in one of the intermediate stages in its synthesis. The desired intermediate ethyl 7-chloro-4-hydroxy 2-quinoline carboxylate was separated from its 5-chloro isomer by fractional crystallisation⁴. The fractionation however, is not complete and considerable amount of the 7-isomer is lost along with the unwanted 5-isomer. 4,7-dichloro 8-nitro quinoline was needed for the present work. It was thought to be of interest to nitrate the crude mixed isomer after the major bulk of ethyl 7-chloro-4-hydroxy 2-quinoline carboxylate had been removed by fractional crystallisation. The nitro-isomers could not be separated by fractional crystallisation and was consequently hydrolysed straight away with 20% NaOH, which effected separation of α -nitro-5-chloro-4-hydroxy quinoline 2-carboxylic acid as its sodium salt during hydrolysis. The corresponding 7-isomer could be obtained by neutralisation of the alkaline solution. Decarboxylation of ethyl α -nitro-7-chloro 4-hydroxy 2-carboxy quinoline may lead to 7-chloro 4-hydroxy (8?)-nitro quinoline, if the nitro group has entered into 8-position of the quinoline ring, which on mechanistic ground seems very likely. All our attempts to decarboxylate the compounds failed and work to establish the position of the nitro group was not further pursued.

EXPERIMENTAL

6,9-Dichloro-triazolo (4,5,1-ij) quinoline-3-ium hydroxide (I):— A solution of sodium nitrite (1.8 g, 0.025 mole) in water (10 ml.) was added dropwise to a mixture of 4,7-dichloro 8-amino quinoline (5.3 g, 0.025 mole) in sulphuric acid (30 ml.1:1) below 5°. After the diazotisation was completed, the excess of sodium nitrite was decomposed with urea and the mixture was stirred for 30 mins. at the same temperature, neutralised with NaHCO₃, filtered, washed thoroughly with water and dried. The compound (4.4 g, 80%) on crystallisation from aqueous ethanol melted at 144-145°. The compound remains unchanged on warming just above the melting point and also on warming with concentrated aqueous ammonia. (Found: C, 45.01; H, 2.65; N, 17.58; C₉H₆Cl₂N₃O requires, C, 44.62; H, 2.06; N, 17.35%).

4,7,8-Trichloro quinoline:— A mixture of 6,9-dichloro triazolo (4,5,1-ij) quinoline-3-ium hydroxide (0.484 g, 0.002 mole), conc. hydrochloric acid (4.5 ml.) and water (3.1 ml.) was cooled to -5° and a suspension of copper powder (0.484 g) in water (3 ml.) was added slowly at that temperature. After keeping at room temperature for 30 mins., the mixture was basified with conc. ammonia and worked up according to the published³ procedure. The solid (0.2 g, 43%) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. = 125-126°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample³ recorded no depression.

4. Surrey and Hammer, *ibid.*, 1946, 68, 115.

4,7-Dichloro-8-hydroxy quinoline:—A suspension of 6,9-dichloro-triazolo (4,5,1-ij) quinoline-3-ium hydroxide (2 g) in water (10 ml.) was adjusted to pH-4 with hydrochloric acid and heated on a steam bath for 2 hrs. The solid was stirred with NaOH to remove some insoluble material. The alkaline solution was neutralised with hydrochloric acid. The precipitated solid (1 g) was collected, washed with water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. m.p.=156-157°C. The reported² melting point is 157-158°.

7-Chloro-8-hydroxy-4-(4'-hydroxyanilino) quinoline (IIa):—(a) A mixture of 6, 9-dichloro triazolo- (4,5,1-ij) quinoline 3-ium hydroxide (4.25 g, 0.0175 mole) p-aminophenol hydrochloride (2.53 g, 0.0175 mole) and water (25 ml.) was heated on a steam bath for 3 hrs., evolution of a gas and frothing took place during the initial period. After keeping for 2 days at room temperature, the solid was collected, washed with water and triturated with ammonia. It was then warmed with ethanol to remove considerable amount (1 g) of insoluble material (m.p. > 350°). The filtrate was diluted with water to turbidity and warmed. On cooling the solid separated out and was crystallised from aqueous ethanol; m.p.=275-276°. (Found: C, 63.02; H, 4.2; N, 10.26; $C_{12}H_{11}Cl N_3O_2$ requires C, 62.82; H, 3.83; N, 0.77 %).

(b) The compound was prepared from 4,7-dichloro 8-hydroxy quinoline (0.214 g, .001 mole) p-aminophenol hydrochloride (0.145 g, .001 mole) and water (7ml.) essentially as described above, m.p.=275-270°; mixed melting point with the sample prepared as in (a) recorded no depression.

(c) A suspension of 7-chloro-8-amino-4 (4'-hydroxyanilino) quinoline (see below) (0.86 g, .003 mole) in sulphuric acid (2 ml.1:1) was diazotised with a solution of $NaNO_2$ (0.267 g, .003 mole) in water (2 ml.) and worked up as described above, m.p.=275-276°; mixed melting point with the compounds prepared as in (a) and (b) recorded no depression. Infra-red spectra of the samples prepared by methods a, b and c were superimposable.

7-Chloro-8-amino 4-(4'-hydroxyanilino) quinoline:—A mixture of 4, 7-dichloro-8-aminoquinoline (0.852 g, .004 mole), p-aminophenol (0.426 g, .004 mole), absolute alcohol (10 ml.) was refluxed for 5 hrs. After cooling the solid was collected, stirred with 5% sodium hydroxide solution. The alkali soluble part was neutralised with dil. HCl. The precipitated solid (0.5 g, 44%) was collected, washed and crystallised from ethanol. m.p.=185-186°. (Found: C, 63.35; H, 4.44; N, 14.79; $C_{13}H_{12}Cl N_3O$ requires C, 63.04; H, 4.20; N, 14.71%).

7-Chloro-8-hydroxy-4-(4'-hydroxyanilino-2-diethylaminomethyl)quinoline (IIc):—2-diethylaminomethyl 4-acetamidophenol (2.84 g, 0.015 mole) was refluxed with 10% sulphuric acid (75 ml.) for one hour. The solution was cooled and adjusted to pH-4 with a 5% solution of sodium hydroxide and then heated on a steam bath with 6,9-dichloro-triazolo-(4,5,1-ij) quinoline 3-ium hydroxide (3,6 g, 0.015 mole) for 2 hrs. After keeping for 2 days at room temperature, the unreacted 6,9-dichloro triazolo-(4,5,1-ij) quinoline 3-ium hydroxide was filtered out and the filtrate was basified with ammonia. The solid collected, washed with water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. (y=2.1 g, 60%) m.p. > 320°. (Found: C, 65.08; H, 6.31; N, 10.98; $C_{20}H_{22}ClN_3O_2$ requires y=C, 64.60; H, 5.82; N, 11.3%).

7-Chloro-8-hydroxy-4 (4'-methoxyanilino) quinoline (IIb):—(a) A mixture of 6,9-dichloro-triazolo- (4,5,1-ij) quinoline-3-ium hydroxide (0.8 g, 0.003 mole), p-anisidine hydro-

chloride (0.53 g, 0.33 mole) were condensed essentially as described earlier. The solid was boiled with ethanol to remove considerable amount of insoluble material. The filtrate cooled and the solid was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p.=168-169°.

(b) A mixture of 4,7-dichloro 8-hydroxy quinoline (0.212 g, .001 mole) p-ansidine hydrochloride (0.147 g, .001 mole) and water (5 ml.) were condensed essentially as described in (a). The solid on crystallisation from aqueous ethanol melted at 168-169°. Mixed melting point with (a) recorded no depression. Infra-red spectra of the samples prepared by method (a) and (b) were superimposable. (Found: C, 63.89; H, 4.75; N, 10.05; $C_{16}H_{13}N_2O_2Cl$ requires C, 63.89; H, 4.32; N, 9.31%).

Nitration of ethyl 4-hydroxy-5 and 7-chloro 2-quinoline carboxylate: The mixed isomer⁴ (25.1g) obtained after the removal of the major bulk of the 7-chloro compound was dissolved in 100% sulphuric acid (81 ml.) and the mixture was thoroughly cooled below 5°. Solid potassium nitrate (11.1 g), was slowly added to the stirred solution during one hour at that temperature. The stirring was continued for a further period of 2 hrs. after the addition was completed, kept overnight in the refrigerator and poured into crushed ice. The solid was collected, washed with cold water and dried in air, yield, 28 g. Several crystallisations from ethanol failed to afford a constant melting compound.

Hydrolysis of ethyl x-nitro-4-hydroxy-5 and 7-chloro 2-quinoline carboxylate:—A mixture of the above crude nitration product (28 g) in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (90 ml.) was heated under reflux for 60 mins. Solid separated out during hydrolysis. The mixture was cooled. The solid was collected, dissolved in water and neutralised with mineral acid to afford 5-chloro-4-hydroxy-x-nitro 2-quinoline carboxylic acid. This was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 315°. (Y; 6.5 g, 22%). (Found: C, 44.88; H, 2.05; N, 10.64; $C_{16}H_{13}Cl N_2O_5$ requires C, 44.89; H, 1.86; N, 10.42%).

The alkaline mother liquor was acidified (congo red) to yield the 7-chloro analogue. This was crystallised from ethanol or acetic acid, m.p. 237-238° (Y; 21g; 77%). Mixed melting point with the carboxylic acid obtained from ethyl 7-chloro-4-hydroxy 2-quinoline carboxylate (see below) recorded no depression. Infra red spectra of the two compounds were superimposable. (Found: C, 43.89; H, 2.08; N, 9.77; $C_{16}H_{13}N_2O_5Cl$ requires C, 44.69; H, 1.86; N, 10.42%).

Nitration of ethyl 7-chloro-4 hydroxy-2-quinoline carboxylate:—Pure ethyl 7-chloro-4-hydroxy-2-quinoline carboxylate (3.7 g) was nitrated with potassium nitrate essentially as described above. The product obtained (80%) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 146-147°.

7-Chloro-4-hydroxy x-nitro 2-quinoline carboxylic acid:—2.5 g of the above nitro compound was refluxed with a 10% solution of sodium hydroxide (8 ml.) for one hr. The clear solution was acidified (congo red) and the precipitated 7-chloro-4-hydroxy-2-quinoline carboxylic acid was collected, washed with water and crystallised from acetic acid or ethanol, m.p. 238° (Y, 2g, 80%).